

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS AND CULTURE IN CHILDREN OF KINDERGARTEN AGE

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Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to prepare children of preschool age for school, to be careful with nature in the process of introducing them to nature, to be kind to the motherland, to implement environmental education and education, to educate young people who have excellent knowledge about nature.*

Keywords: *natural beauty, mental, moral, physical, economic, ecological, aesthetic, education, educator, skill, educational opportunity.*

The role of environmental education in ensuring the harmony between nature and man is extremely large. Continuous environmental education and upbringing, which is carried out at all stages of the educational system, requires the formation of new relationships with the nature of man, as well as with himself. This, in turn, can serve as a foundation for the formation of a well-rounded person. Cultivating love for nature leads to education in the spirit of respect for the motherland, its natural monuments, historical monuments, traditions of our people, and the formation of a highly spiritual person.

Educating preschool children to be careful is one of the most important tasks of preschool educational institutions. In the process of introducing children to nature, great attention is paid to inculcating a careful attitude towards nature.

Only if children acquire at least the first knowledge about nature, learn simple methods of growing plants, taking care of animals, observe nature, and see its beauty, they will have care and concern for nature. It will be an opportunity to cultivate a positive attitude.

It is at this time that children develop love for nature, their beloved country, and their motherland.

Y. A. Komensky compared the 4 types of schools to the 4 seasons of the year. "School of Mothers" reminds of a wonderful spring covered with fragrant plants, buds and flowers.

Mother tongue school is like summer and some early ripe fruits. In "Gymnasium" it reminds of the autumn season, when the rich harvest from the fields, gardens and poplars is collected and stored in the "treasure of the mind".

And finally, the "Academy" is likened to a person who distributes the harvest with the intention of spending it throughout his life.

Y.A. Comenius recommended learning 18 subjects at the Mother School. According to him, a six-year-old boy:

water, earth, air, fire, rain, snow, ice, stone, iron, tree, grass, bird, fish;

- the difference between light and darkness, knowledge about the sky, sun, moon, and stars, imaginations about their daily rising and setting;

- he should know what a mountain, valley, field, river, village, city is according to the characteristics of the place where he lives. Y. A. Komensky explained everything in connection with nature. In order to attract the attention of readers, he named the books interestingly and fully expressed their content. He says that the most beautiful thing in this area is to sample the different views of the garden.[1. 12.b]

The content of the work of introducing children to nature is highlighted, and directions for the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities to have ideas about animate and inanimate nature, the earth, the world of animals, and the world of plants are defined. These requirements can be fulfilled only when children are first introduced to the nature of the countries that are dear to them, where they were born and raised, because the formation of the knowledge of a preschool child is carried out in the process of direct interaction with the environment that surrounds him. is increased.

Environmental education of children of preschool age is important, and at this age, the foundations of personal ecological culture, which is considered a part of spiritual culture, are formed in a child. Environmental education of children is a goal-oriented pedagogical process.

It is characterized by environmental education of the person, a positive approach to nature protection relations, the discipline directed from the point of view of environmental protection in the implementation of activities related to nature, and the emergence of ecological consciousness.

Environmental culture of a person is the result of ecological education. In the preschool age, the component of the child's personal ecological culture is the knowledge of nature and its orientation from the point of view of ecology.

Mental and aesthetic attitudes towards nature are closely related to the content of the knowledge acquired by the child. Knowledge related to ecological content guides children's activities in nature and their self-control, discipline and directs them towards the goal. Knowledge of the laws of nature, which are sufficiently accessible to children's perception, occupies a special place in the formation of an attitude towards nature. The development of attitude towards nature (life situations such as classes, excursions, walks) is closely related to the organization of a pedagogical process based on the child's spiritual and positive spiritual experiences.[20.b]

An educator should be able to make a child feel pity for a living creature, to protect it, to enjoy it when meeting living nature, to be happy, surprised, to be proud of what he has done, and to be satisfied.

In pre-school educational institutions, children are introduced to nature and the changes that occur in it in different seasons of the year. On the basis of the acquired knowledge, qualities such as the ability to clearly understand natural phenomena, to be curious, to observe, to think logically, and to look at living things with pleasure are formed. Loving nature, respecting it carefully, taking care of living animals not only arouses interest in nature, but also inculcates patriotism, hard work in children, honoring and multiplying natural resources of adults. it also opens the way to forming the best characteristics, such as treating one's work with respect.[23 b]

Children are happy with the results of their work in nature, they show their friendly attitude towards nature.

After taking care of various creatures and plants, the children who are being educated in pre-school educational institutions, their mood will rise and they will receive spiritual

nourishment. By reading books about nature to children, knowledge, skills and abilities about nature are improved.

Environmental education is important for preschool children to become ecologically cultured adults.

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